

1 Transforming wastewater treatment plants into reclaimed water facilities in water-unbalanced
2 regions. An overview of possibilities and recommendations focusing on the Italian case.

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8 Keywords: wastewater treatment; water management; water reuse; water scarcity; water utilities.

9 Abstract

10 Water scarcity will be one of the most challenging topics to cope with in the following years,
11 especially in the regions most affected by climate change such as the Mediterranean basin. The
12 implementation of water reuse practices thus appears essential to satisfy future water demands in
13 a sustainable way, helping to reduce hydric stress in water-unbalanced regions. However, it remains
14 as an underused practice. To change this situation, the wastewater sector needs to develop some
15 structural changes that include not only the transformation of conventional wastewater treatment
16 plants (WWTPs) into novel reclaimed water facilities (RWF), but also some paradigm shifts regarding
17 social, political and legal factors. The goal of this manuscript is to provide a systemic, novel and
18 updated vision of the wastewater treatment sector and to give some recommendations for the
19 implementation of wastewater reuse in agriculture, with a special focus on the Italian case.
20 Extensive data regarding water reuse technologies for the refining, disinfection and advanced
21 oxidation of wastewater is also provided. This comprehensive analysis could help to align the
22 objectives to be achieved from all the perspectives (technical, economic, legal and socio-political),
23 thus helping to fill current gaps and overcome barriers that hinder water reuse development.

24

25 1. Introduction

26 Currently, global population accounts for 7.7 billion people, a number that is expected to increase
27 up to 9 billion by 2050 (UNESCO, 2020a). Apart from this, current water demand per capita is also
28 raising due to global increase in the quality of life and the population expectations. Moreover,
29 natural water availability is getting scarcer due to increasing effects related to climate change issues
30 (heatwaves, drought periods, etc.) and the high level of water pollution (EIT Water Scarcity, 2021).
31 In fact, less than 40% of urban water bodies are in good ecological and chemical status (EEA, 2018).
32 As a consequence, many countries are expected to have noticeable difficulties to cope with water
33 demands in future decades. In this respect, the Water Exploitation Index (WEI) of a country is an
34 indicator of the pressure of the population on natural water resources, being Cyprus, Greece, Spain,
35 Turkey, Czech Republic and Malta (in this order) the European countries presenting the highest
36 values, ranging from 20 to 45% (Aquastat, 2020), so they are considered to be very stressed. Italy
37 occupies the sixth place with a WEI of around 17% (mid stressed). However, this value is influenced
38 by the significant differences between the north and the south parts of the country, being some
39 Southern regions in severe water stressed conditions. This situation is predicted to worsen
40 significantly in the incoming years, being over half of EU river basins expected to be affected by
41 water scarcity by 2030 (WRE, 2022).

42 Apart from limiting water resources for human consumption, water scarcity implies some
43 environmental impacts such as aquifer exhaustion from over abstraction, salinisation of
44 groundwater, increased erosion of cultivated soils on slopes and decrease of biodiversity in natural
45 water bodies. These impacts are not well documented in many EU member states but different case
46 studies have shown that over-abstraction and salinisation of aquifers due to saltwater intrusion
47 occur in many parts of the Mediterranean coastlines of Italy, Spain, and Turkey, as well as in some
48 localised areas in Northern Europe (MED-EUWI, 2007). It must be noted that irrigation is normally

49 the main cause of water overexploitation in those regions, accounting for around 70-80% of the
50 total water consumed (Ofori et al., 2021; UNESCO, 2020b). New sources of water thus need to be
51 found to alleviate water scarcity trends. In this respect, the reuse of wastewater in irrigation is a
52 practice that could help to cope with future demands in a sustainable way, also increasing circular
53 economy in the water sector (EIT Water Scarcity, 2021; Foglia et al., 2021).

54 Wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) could be an important source of water since around 312
55 million megalitres of municipal wastewater are estimated to be produced worldwide each year
56 (Pikaar et al., 2022). Non-conventional water resources like reclaimed water (i.e., water obtained
57 from reusing wastewater) thus present enormous potential to be used for non-drinking purposes
58 such as irrigation, which would reduce the high hydric pressure caused by the agricultural sector. It
59 must be highlighted that, apart from reclaimed water, other resources such as nutrients, cellulose,
60 biopolymers and fertilisers can be recovered from wastewater, with the subsequent increase in the
61 profitability and sustainability of the process (Palmieri et al., 2019; Robles et al., 2021). However,
62 conventional WWTPs have been traditionally designed as final barriers of urban water pollution,
63 often hindering the possibility to recover all these valuable resources present in their effluents (EEA,
64 2022; Seco et al., 2018a). Furthermore, due to factors such as diffuse pollution in origin, punctual
65 malfunctions, limited treatment capacities and combined sewage overflows (between others),
66 WWTP are not always able to accomplish legal limits, which produces environmental and social
67 problems (mainly) in the surroundings and in downstream locations (Crocetti et al., 2021). In
68 addition, there are increasing concerns in the wastewater treatment sector regarding greenhouse
69 gases (GHG) emissions during treatment processes and the discharge (within WWTP effluents) of
70 contaminants of emerging concern (CEC) such as pharmaceuticals, antibiotics, endocrine disruptors,
71 microplastics, and antibiotic resistance bacteria (ARB) (Marinelli et al., 2021b; Tran et al., 2018; Wu
72 et al., 2022). WWTPs will be required to reduce these emissions in the recent future, thus it can be

73 stated that the wastewater treatment sector needs to be transformed and modernised to satisfy
 74 current societal and environmental demands and to increase circularity in the water sector (EEA,
 75 2022; Radini et al., 2022). For this transformation to occur, the wastewater sector needs to be
 76 approached from different perspectives, considering technological, techno-economic, socio-
 77 political and legal aspects in a comprehensive way (Figure 1).
 78 Following these remarks, the goal of this manuscript is to evaluate the current state of the
 79 wastewater treatment sector and to give some recommendations that could boost the
 80 implementation of wastewater reuse practices. To this aim, the evaluation and comparison of water
 81 reuse technologies to produce reclaimed water will be done in Section 2. Section 3 will describe the
 82 pillars on which the transformation of the wastewater treatment sector could (or should) be based.
 83 In Section 4, the water reuse sector in Italy will be analysed. Italy has a powerful water sector that
 84 generates 17% of Italian GDP, being one of the most water-intensive countries in Europe (The
 85 European House - Ambrosetti, 2022). In addition, the interest in wastewater reuse is projected to
 86 continue expanding in the following years in this water-unbalanced country (EIT Water Scarcity,
 87 2021; WRE, 2022), so it was selected as representative case to be evaluated.

88

89 *Figure 1. Factors that influence the transformation of the wastewater treatment sector to implement*
90 *water reuse.*

91

92 2. Water reuse technologies

93 Conventional WWTPs have traditionally aimed at the removal of the organic matter, suspended
94 solids and nutrients, with less focus on microbial contamination, GHG emissions and the discharge
95 of CEC, since, in a common linear economy perspective, the main objective of wastewater treatment
96 was only the compliance with legal discharge requirements (EEA, 2022). This approach is slowly
97 shifting towards a circular economy approach, considering wastewater treatment as a process to
98 recover reclaimed water (and other resources) from wastewater (Pikaar et al., 2022; Robles et al.,
99 2021). But there are still multiple barriers that hinder this transition (Radini et al., 2022), so they
100 must be systematically overcome. One of these barriers is that there exist few WWTPs that are
101 currently able to achieve the high water-quality standards of “EU Regulation 741/2020 on minimum
102 requirements for water reuse”. Particularly, the new European regulation for water reuse regulation
103 requires higher standards for disinfection, lower content of solids (i.e., total suspended solids) and
104 organic matter (i.e., BOD₅ concentration) in the final effluent than those required for the simple
105 discharge of wastewater in surface water bodies. In addition, the regulation on water reuse requires
106 risk assessment for the identification of all potential hazards for the environment and human health,
107 which may comprise the removal of micropollutants and priority substances (Radini et al., 2022). In
108 fact, removal of CECs from wastewater is subject of debate worldwide and is included in the draft
109 of future directives, while some countries such as Switzerland (after the implementation of a new
110 Water Protection Act in 2016) and Germany (two federal states on voluntary basis) have already
111 implemented legal requirements for CEC removal. Consequently, innovative water post-treatment
112 technologies are needed to be implemented. This implies extra costs and difficulties (due to new

113 infrastructures and operation and maintenance labours) that could disincentive water reuse
114 practices (Ofori et al., 2021). Planning and design of treatment solutions to reach the appropriate
115 objective is thus crucial to ensure the feasibility and the implementation of water reuse practices.
116 For this reason, in Section 2, an overview of possible post-treatment technologies to transform
117 current wastewater treatment plants into RWF schemes is presented.

118

119 2.1. Refining technologies

120 Effluents from current WWTPs normally contain significant amounts of suspended solids (that can
121 reach up to $30 \text{ mgSS}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$), organic matter, pathogens and other emerging contaminants (Tran et al.,
122 2018). Despite these levels of contaminants can accomplish current legal requirements for
123 discharging, they often make them not suitable for reuse in agriculture. In addition, they can hinder
124 further disinfection (Section 2.2) and emerging contaminants removal (Section 2.3). The refinement
125 of wastewater for further post-treatment can be done by two different approaches: i) implementing
126 conventional wastewater treatment processes with tertiary treatment processes to “extra-polish”
127 wastewater, thus accomplishing water reuse legal requirements; ii) to substitute current
128 wastewater treatment schemes by novel, more circular and greener treatment processes based on
129 more sustainable processes such as anaerobic-based treatments, nature-based solutions (NBS), etc.
130 (González-Camejo et al., 2021; Rosemarin et al., 2020; Seco et al., 2018a; Thompson et al., 2022).
131 To polish WWTP secondary effluents, simple technologies based on the physical removal of
132 pollutants are commonly used, such as a sand filters (González Camejo et al., 2022). Apart from
133 removing macro-pollutants such as suspended solids, these technologies have been reported to be
134 able to subtract certain amounts of some CECs such as microplastics and other chemical substances
135 (Table 1). However, the water quality that could be obtained with these systems is limited. If higher
136 reclaimed water quality is needed, membrane-based systems are a better option.

137 Membrane treatment allows the physical retention of pollutants in one side of the membrane, while
138 “clean” water permeate flows through the other side. High-quality effluents can be thus reached,
139 with almost no solids and high removals of pathogenic bacteria and viruses (González-Camejo et al.,
140 2019; Zhang et al., 2022). Due to their high performances in microbial and solids removal, coupled
141 with their flexibility on achieving fit-for-purpose water quality by selecting the most appropriate
142 pore size, this technology is growing higher interest in reuse applications. Membranes can be used
143 both as tertiary treatment (after conventional wastewater treatment systems), or being part of
144 alternative wastewater treatment processes, as occurs in aerobic membrane bioreactors (MBRs)
145 (Grandclément et al., 2017; Iglesias et al., 2017), anaerobic membrane bioreactors (AnMBRs) (Foglia
146 et al., 2020; Seco et al., 2018a), or in other innovative processes that have been recently
147 implemented to boost circularity in the water sector such as microalgae-based membrane
148 photobioreactors (González-Camejo et al., 2021). Although treatment efficacy of membrane-
149 systems also depends on wastewater, microorganisms and solids characteristics, the main factor
150 affecting filtration is normally the membrane pore size. Lower sizes will improve removal efficiency,
151 but they will also increase membrane fouling, which is the main issue of membrane-based systems
152 (Qasim et al., 2018). Different membrane-based technologies can be distinguished according to
153 their pore size. Microfiltration (MF) and ultrafiltration (UF) are commonly applied barriers for solids
154 and pathogens, being able to remove them to a very high extent (Table 1). Depending on the
155 reclaimed water quality required (Class A, B, C or D, according to EU Regulation 2020/741 (European
156 Parliament, 2020)), one membrane-based technology or another would be recommended.
157 However, the capital and operational costs of membrane-based systems tend to be elevated, due
158 to the high pressures required to ensure the correct flow and to avoid membrane fouling, as well as
159 for membrane cleanings (Seco et al., 2018a). Moreover, membrane operations are more complex
160 than other wastewater tertiary treatment systems and thus, they have to be carefully operated. On

161 the other hand, dynamic membranes (DM) appear as an alternative cheaper membrane-based
162 system. Unlike other membrane systems, the main filtering actor in DMs are cake layer formed
163 during the continuous filtration. Consequently, water quality is not constant during time, but
164 depends on the state of the cake layer, which can be controlled by physical cleaning methods
165 (Sanchis-Perucho et al., 2022). Depending on the membrane pore sizes and the quality class of
166 reclaimed water, WRF schemes can include other downstream post-treatments (either immediately
167 after membranes or/and in the storage and distribution infrastructures) in order to assure health
168 and environmental safety production and storage of reclaimed water according to EU Regulation
169 2020/741. In these cases, the previous membrane filtration could ease the disinfection (Section 2.2)
170 and advanced treatment processes (Section 2.3) significantly, so it is recommended as long as OPEX
171 and CAPEX of membranes are not excessive.

172 Another alternative to conventional WWTPs are nature-based solutions (NBS) such as waste
173 stabilisation ponds (WSPs), green filters and constructed wetlands (CWs), including vertical
174 subsurface flow (VF) CWs, horizontal subsurface flow (HF) CWs, and free water surface (FWS) CW.
175 This group of technologies aim to reduce the impacts of wastewater treatment by imitating natural
176 environments, thus showing minimal energy requirements during their operations (since mechanical
177 aeration is not required (Garfí et al., 2017), simplicity, and low environmental impacts in the
178 construction phase (Kobayashi et al., 2020; Lam et al., 2015).

179 NBS have been confirmed to be robust and low-cost eco-technologies for wastewater treatment
180 and reuse, being ideal for the implementation of water reuse practices in small communities and
181 other decentralised systems (Carvalho et al., 2022; Kaliakatsos et al., 2019). Regarding centralised
182 wastewater treatment systems, NBS can be also an alternative to conventional WWTPs, being able
183 to treat different wastewater streams such as raw municipal wastewater, primary- or secondary-
184 treated wastewater, grey, black and rain wastewater, etc. They often show high removal of macro-

185 pollutants and pathogens (Table 1), especially in the summer season (Faleschini et al., 2012; Otter
186 et al., 2020; Russo et al., 2019). However, they are not usually very efficient in CEC removal and
187 commonly require huge land surfaces. Combinations of NBS with other manmade treatments can
188 thus be an option to produce reclaimed water with the appropriate quality level of irrigation in and
189 efficient and environmentally friendly way (Lutterbeck et al., 2020; Thompson et al., 2022).
190 Summarising, the implementation of refining technologies in WRF schemes could be advisable to
191 improve efficiencies in further downstream water reuse processes. However, depending on
192 wastewater characteristics and the costs and impacts of the refining technologies, they might not
193 be needed as their operation could be unfeasible.

194 [TABLE 1 NEAR HERE]

195

196 2.2. Disinfection technologies

197 To ensure microbiological quality, disinfection treatment is essential during wastewater reuse
198 applications. Conventional chemical-based treatments that have been applied at full scale for
199 wastewater disinfection include, between others, ultraviolet (UV) radiation, ozone (O₃), peracetic
200 acid (PAA) and Performic Acid (PFA) (Collivignarelli et al., 2018). Apart from them, chlorination (e.g.,
201 by addition of NaClO) is one of the most well-established disinfection techniques due to its reliability
202 and simplicity (Collivignarelli et al., 2018). However, it is commonly dismissed for production of
203 high-quality reclaimed water since, high chlorine doses, in presence of natural organic substances,
204 produces different disinfection byproducts (DBPs), such as trihalomethanes (THMs) and haloacetic
205 acids, known to be carcinogenic to humans and toxic to aquatic life (Richardson and Ternes, 2022).
206 Furthermore, if ammonia is present in water, the formation of chloramines can lead to the
207 formation of the highly toxic nitrosamines, and particularly N-Nitrosodimethylamine (NDMA) (Sgroi
208 et al., 2018). Chlorine dioxide is another bactericidal agent which disinfectant power is even higher

209 than chlorine. ClO_2 is a yellow-green gas with a pungent smell, water-soluble, but very unstable. It
210 is produced in site by the reaction of sodium hypochlorite with hydrochloric acid (Collivignarelli et
211 al., 2018). Chlorite (ClO_2^-) and chlorate (ClO_3^-) are the major reaction by-products, which are
212 regulated during drinking water production. On the contrary, the formation of THMs is significantly
213 reduced (Al-Otoum et al., 2016).

214 As most convenient alternative, PAA has been adopted in many WWTPs due to: i) the easy retrofit
215 of the already existing equipment for chlorination (without the need for expensive capital
216 investment); ii) its bactericidal, virucidal, fungicidal, and sporicidal effectiveness (as demonstrated
217 in various industries); iii) its broad spectrum of activity even in the presence of heterogeneous
218 organic matter; iv) absence of persistent toxic or mutagenic residuals or by-products; v) no
219 quenching requirements; vi) small dependence on pH; vii) short contact time and; viii) effectiveness
220 for treating primary and secondary effluents (Domínguez Henao et al., 2018; Kitis, 2004).
221 Nevertheless, high residual PAA concentration ($> 2 \text{ mg}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$) in the effluent is commonly reason of
222 significant toxic effects in aquatic ecosystems. PAA is typically commercially available at 5-40% w/w
223 in an equilibrium mixture with acetic acid, H_2O_2 , and water. Although H_2O_2 is also a disinfectant
224 contributing to the disinfection power of the PAA mixture, acetic acid (AA) is a more potent
225 antimicrobial agent than H_2O_2 . PAA disinfection action is very effective, and its use results to be very
226 competitive with other benchmark technologies including chlorination and UV irradiation. Major
227 disadvantage associated with peracetic acid disinfection is the increase of organic content in the
228 effluent due to acetic acid and thus in the potential microbial regrowth. The formation of adsorbable
229 organic halogens (AOX) has been also reported (Antonelli et al., 2013)

230 Tertiary treatment with performic acid (PFA) is a relatively recent option for chemical disinfection
231 that has been already tested in different applications including advanced primary effluent, storm
232 water, and secondary effluent treatment (Falsanisi et al., 2010; Karpova et al., 2013). Despite not

233 being as well established as the previous ones, it generally implies the formation of by-products
234 such as formic acid, CH₄ and CO₂, which at the concentration levels commonly encountered are
235 considered non-toxic (Tchobanoglous et al., 2014). Generally, PFA showed greater microbial
236 inactivation properties than other organic peracids (such as peracetic acid (PAA) and perpropionic
237 acid) against faecal indicator bacteria (i.e., E. coli, fecal coliforms and enterococci) in water and
238 wastewater. Importantly, no genotoxic or mutagenic substances were detected in PFA-disinfected
239 wastewater in a full-scale municipal study (Maffettone et al., 2020).

240 Last but not least, UV disinfection is cited in most guidelines as the “best available technology not
241 entailing excessive costs” for reclaimed water production (Collivignarelli et al., 2018; Lazarova et al.,
242 1999). In fact, its O&M costs are even lower than PPA and chlorination when high quality must be
243 guaranteed as in the case of wastewater reuse (Reclaimed water quality class A in EU Regulation
244 2020/741: 10 CFU/100ml). For this reason, it presents nowadays a great diffusion. UV disinfection
245 is effective for the inactivation of most viruses, spores and cystis, and in general, needs shorter
246 contact time (about 20 – 30 s for low-pressure lamps) with respect to other solutions. Furthermore,
247 it is compact, with low efforts required from operators, even if maintenance is required to control
248 fouling of tubes, which also makes it suitable for decentralised systems. Since it is a physical process,
249 it avoids the use of hazardous or corrosive chemicals, does not require additional safety measures
250 for handling, transport, and storage, and does not generate residuals potentially toxic for human or
251 aquatic life <https://doi.org/10.3390/su10010086>(Collivignarelli et al., 2018). However, as stated in
252 Section 2.1, suspended solids and turbidity can obstacle UV radiation, significantly losing its
253 effectiveness when wastewater contains SS concentrations over 30 mg·L⁻¹. A refinement treatment
254 is thus advisable to be installed before UV disinfection.

255 A summary of reported disinfection technologies for pathogen removal in municipal WWTP
256 effluents can be found in Table 2. It must be noted that depending on the dose, some disinfection
257 technologies such as UV and ozonation could be also able to remove CEC (Section 2.3).

258 [TABLE 2 NEAR HERE]

259

260 2.3. Advanced treatment technologies

261 Advanced oxidation processes (AOPs) are treatments that mainly aim to chemically destroy
262 contaminants of emerging concern, which are present at ppb levels in water. Disinfection of
263 pathogen simultaneously occurs. AOPs can be developed by simultaneously applying different
264 oxidants, including ozone, hydrogen peroxide, UV radiation, peracetic acid, chlorine, etc., normally
265 in higher doses than those used only for disinfection (Table 3). This, together with the large amounts
266 of wastewater treated in WWTPs, imply that AOPs normally present high operating costs, which has
267 somewhat limited their large-scale applications (Collivignarelli et al., 2018; Miklos et al., 2018). In
268 addition, the formation of reaction reactants with high reactivity, such as hydroxyl radicals (OH•)
269 can occur. To overcome these issues, some authors have tested processes such solar Photo-Fenton
270 with the goal to use solar radiation as main oxidising factor. However, this process is limited by the
271 daylight hours, thus storage tanks would be needed to store wastewaters produced during night
272 hours. Moreover, acid conditions are mandatory for solar phot-Fenton processes to reduce the
273 presence of inorganic carbon as bicarbonate, which tends to slow down the process (Arzate et al.,
274 2019; Pignatello et al., 2006).

275 When looking only at micropollutants oxidation, ozonation (and its combinations O₃/H₂O₂, O₃/UV)
276 appear as the most energy efficient processes with consumptions under 1 kWh·m⁻³, while processes
277 such as photocatalysis, ultrasound, and microwave-based AOPs have reported energy consumptions
278 over under 100 kWh·m⁻³, being thus considered not energy efficient for water reuse (Miklos et al.,

279 2018). On the other hand, AOPs based on combinations of technologies with UV irradiation (e.g.,
280 UV/H₂O₂, H₂O₂/O₃/UV) have been reported as the most effective processes for wastewater
281 treatment that produce negligible or null amount of DBPs (Candido et al., 2017; Pérez-Moya et al.,
282 2017; Sgroi et al., 2021b). Technologies based on granular (GAC) and powder activated carbon (PAC)
283 can be also used to remove CECs (Table 3). It must be noted that membrane-based technologies
284 such as nanofiltration (NF), which presents smaller pore sizes than MF and UF, could be theoretically
285 as “perfect filters” that could remove CECs (Arvaniti et al., 2022; Mamo et al., 2018). However, the
286 costs of NF are commonly too high, thus the applications for reclaimed water production are limited
287 nowadays.

288 [TABLE 3 NEAR HERE]

289

290 2.4. Indicators for water reuse technologies

291 To select the most appropriate water reuse technologies, the following factors should be taken into
292 consideration: i) characteristics of infrastructures and their management; ii) performances in
293 pollutant removal; iii) reagent (or radiation) dose; iv) affecting parameters; v) downstream effects;
294 and vi) costs. For the water reuse technologies evaluated in Section 2, Table 4 shows a summary of
295 these main key performance indicators. It has to be considered that this information can only serve
296 as a general guideline since these factors will also depend on other parameters that are related to
297 each water treatment case, for instance, on the number of inhabitants served, the price of energy
298 and reagents of the region, local legislation, land requirements, etc.

299 [TABLE 4 NEAR HERE]

300

301 Apart from the KPI indicators shown in Table 4, Environmental Indicators (EIs) obtained through LCA
302 analysis are essential to evaluate the environmental impacts that those water reuse technologies

303 can present (Foglia et al., 2021). In this respect, Table 5 shows some values of global warming
304 potential (GWP), energy consumption, acidification, ozone depletion potential (ODP), Abiotic
305 Depletion Potential (ADP), Freshwater Eutrophication Potential (FEP), Marine eutrophication
306 Potential (MEP), and Ecotoxicity potential (ETP) for some water reuse technologies described in
307 Section 2.

308 The first thing that has to be taken into account is that reusing reclaimed water has been reported
309 to show some environmental benefits in comparison to directly discharge the treated water (Foglia
310 et al., 2021; Jiménez-Benítez et al., 2020). Moreover, as additional processes of WWTP, post-
311 treatments do not often influence significantly the whole environmental impact of the overall
312 wastewater treatment process (Meneses et al., 2010). In a very general way, data displayed in Table
313 5 shows that NBS normally present the lowest values of the EI evaluated, while membrane systems
314 tend to show the highest values due to air sparging needs and the chemical reagents used for
315 membrane cleaning (Pretel et al., 2016). With respect to chlorination, ozonation, UV, AOPs and GAC
316 technologies, EIs are normally in the same range (Table 5). It must be noted that, for chemical-based
317 treatments, the transport of reagents is normally the main contributor to environmental impacts,
318 while energy consumption is the most relevant impact for UV scenario (Foglia et al., 2021). For the
319 GAC system, it is relevant that 81% of GWP is generated from the production of GAC, which is
320 reduced to only 20% of GWP when GAC production occurs after reusing regenerated adsorbent
321 (Jeswani et al., 2015).

322 Summarising, there is no universal technical solutions since all the cited water reuse technologies
323 present some strong and weak characteristics. Each water reuse scheme must be therefore adapted to
324 each specific scenario by combining some of these technologies in the most efficient way (SgROI et al.,
325 2021a; Shi et al., 2021). But it must be noted that some combinations of water reuse technologies
326 could significantly increase treatment costs and environmental impacts. By means of example, the

327 coupling of UF with UV technologies evaluated by Carre et al. (2017) was significantly more
328 impacting than single UV since electricity consumption was nearly doubled.

329 [TABLE 5 NEAR HERE]

330

331 3. Transformation of the wastewater treatment sector beyond treatment technologies

332 Apart from the technological transformation of WWTPs, a complete and systemic transformation of
333 the wastewater sector is essential to increase its sustainability and capacity to satisfy water
334 demands of the future. This implies that, apart from improving wastewater treatment schemes with
335 water reuse technologies (Section 2), other techno-economic, legal, political and social aspects need
336 to be approached and aligned with the principles of sustainability and circular economy to overcome
337 the current barriers that hinder the wide development of water reuse practices (EEA, 2022;
338 Goodwin et al., 2019; Radini et al., 2022).

339

340 3.1. Techno-economic aspects

341 One of the main elements to be improved to increase reclaimed water production is the number of
342 reuse facilities that are able to treat wastewater with the appropriate quality in a feasible way, but
343 it is widely known that this implies significant investment and operating costs increases (Table 4).
344 Moreover, the modifications needed to transform WWTPs into RWFs go beyond adding post-
345 treatment technologies to increase pollutant removal. These facilities should also arrange storage
346 infrastructures, piping systems, adequate and instructed personnel (Radini et al., 2022). These
347 amendments entail some extra costs and difficulties that could discourage water utilities to invest
348 in water reuse production (Goodwin et al., 2019). It is thus important that WRFs not only aim to
349 produce reclaimed water from wastewater, but also to recover other resources contained in
350 wastewater (such as nutrients, cellulose, biopolimers and fertilisers) in order to maximise the

351 revenues obtained from the process (Palmieri et al., 2019; Pikaar et al., 2022). It must be noted that
352 this implementation of reclaimed water production and resource recovery from wastewater will not
353 be boosted if WRFs are only managed by conventional knowledge-based practices. The
354 transformation of the wastewater treatment sector to water-smart RWFs through the improvement
355 of digitalisation of the plants is essential to improve process performance and reduce malfunctions
356 (Water Europe, 2022).

357 From a techno-economic point of view, powerful digital technologies have the potential to develop
358 predictive maintenance, extending the life of the infrastructure; to optimise the workforce and
359 increase the efficiency in capital management; to reduce operating expenses and increased cash
360 flow through more management of investments; to reduce the possibility of making mistakes and
361 to foster greater speed in decision-making due to the rapidity in data processing; and to detect
362 malfunctions and anomalies in the WRF operation (Fernandez de Canete et al., 2021; Foschi et al.,
363 2021; Pisa et al., 2019). All these improvements can also (indirectly) help to protect the environment
364 by reducing pollutant and GHG emissions, energy losses and resource consumption of the process.
365 Furthermore, digital tools can improve notably the management of water infrastructures, the
366 quality of service provided to citizens and the levels of awareness and collaboration between
367 utilities, authorities and citizens (ICT4Water and EC, 2018; The European House - Ambrosetti, 2022).
368 However, the transition to digital wastewater sector is mainly restrained by: i) the lack of business
369 cases and tangible evidences of the benefits provided by digital solutions at each level of
370 management across the water value chain; ii) the low level of maturity of some digital solutions
371 (ICT4Water and EC, 2020, 2018); iii) the commonly high investment needed to acquire digital tools
372 and the efforts to be done to train the personnel and to keep digitals systems updated; iv)
373 unsympathetically regulatory landscape and; v) low consumer demand, which is influenced by the
374 fact that digital R&D advances do not always match with 'on-the-ground' reality.

375 Technological development, awareness on the benefits of digital tools as well as economic and
376 political support to water utilities are thus expected to implement this digital transition in the water
377 sector, which is essential to implement water reuse practices (Radini et al., 2022).

378

379 3.2. Socio-Political aspects

380 Water policies can play a highly significant role in reducing the techno-economic barriers
381 commented in Section 3.1 with the goal to shift to a more sustainable wastewater sector. For
382 instance, economic instruments such as full-cost recovery (which is part of the ‘polluter-pays
383 principle’) can help to partially finance existing and future water infrastructures by obtaining higher
384 funding directly from the water bill, thus reducing the investment pressure of water utilities. There
385 is global consensus on the advantages of cost recovery policies to deal with water scarcity issues
386 since, apart from increasing financial resources for investments in RWF infrastructures, it also
387 achieves water saving through water pricing (Berbel et al., 2019; EIT Water Scarcity, 2021). In fact,
388 it has been proved that EU countries with higher water prices normally consume less amount of
389 water per capita than those with lower prices (The European House - Ambrosetti, 2022).

390 Other water policy-based tools such as green public procurement (GPP) and EU Taxonomy can
391 increase the benefits of water utilities that turn their treatment processes into more circular and
392 greener ones by giving them some economic and/or competitive advantages in comparison to those
393 non-sustainable companies, hence encouraging utilities to to give more priority (and higher
394 investment) to the transition to WRFs. GPP approach goes beyond current public procurement that
395 simply focuses on satisfying low-cost approach, obviating sustainability, and gets the public buyer
396 become an early adopter by buying (or hiring) a product, service or process that contains
397 substantially novel and environmentally friendly characteristics (EC, 2021a, 2021b; EIT Water
398 Scarcity, 2021). On the other hand, the EU taxonomy is a classification tool that provides information

399 to investors about how “environmentally sustainable” an economic activity is (f.i. reclaimed water
400 production), preventing greenwashing and helping investors to make more circular and greener
401 choices (EC, 2021a; Traini, 2021). The requirements to define an economic activity as
402 environmentally sustainable according to the EU taxonomy have been described by TEG (2020).

403 But for all these policies to attain their goals, it is essential to raise awareness about all issues related
404 to water scarcity, water reuse and the current situation of the water management sector. Normally,
405 when referred to wastewater reuse, there is a common perception of risk that often discourages its
406 use. To minimise this barrier, EU Regulation 741/2020 requires the elaboration of water reuse risk
407 management plans (WRRMPs) with the goal to assure the safe use of reclaimed water, thus helping
408 to shift this common vision (Radini et al., 2022). Moreover, in water-unbalanced regions like those
409 of Southern Europe, there is often a misleading concept related to thinking of reclaimed water as a
410 source of water that has to compete with freshwater sources in the market (hence demanding it
411 the same quality and prices than to potable water). This conventional vision is influenced by the fact
412 that in many Southern Europe countries, the potable water prices are lower than the EU average
413 (The European House - Ambrosetti, 2022). Consequently, consumers do not feel water as a scarce
414 resource and tend to opt for other alternative freshwater sources such as groundwater and water
415 from river transfers, obviating many sustainability and water scarcity issues associated to these
416 practices (Jiménez-Benítez et al., 2020). In other words, current water market in Southern Europe
417 does not properly take into account the “real” value of reclaimed water, which lies on reducing the
418 use of limited freshwater water resources, complementing them to satisfying the whole water
419 demand without increasing hydric pressures on the environment (Water Europe, 2022).

420 This misleading vision is probably related to the fact that the water sector (as well as others) has
421 been conventionally managed as an isolated pillar, obviating the interdependencies between water
422 and energy, food, climate, and other relevant sectors. This often leads to biased management and

423 political decisions. For this, it is of highly importance to change the way the water sector is managed,
424 avoiding the “silo” thinking and moving to the Nexus approach (Flammini et al., 2014). Nexus
425 approach entails a shift of paradigm in wastewater management, from simply considering
426 environmental pollution related to wastewater discharges to assessing all the impacts (positive or
427 negative) related to treatment processes with the ultimate goals of achieving carbon neutrality and
428 the conservation of ecosystems and biodiversity. Hence, nexus thinking is highly advisable when
429 developing novel water treatment technologies, water management strategies and water-related
430 policies and research programmes (Albrecht et al., 2018; Marinelli et al., 2021a; Radini et al., 2022,
431 2021).

432

433 3.3. Legal aspects

434 As typically occurs in environment-related topics such as wastewater treatment, legislation plays a
435 highly significant role that often defines (either on purpose or indirectly) the structure of water
436 management schemes, including the development of certain practices. In this respect, excessive
437 legal requirements often act as a barrier to implement water reuse practices and to close water
438 loops (Cipolletta et al., 2021; Radini et al., 2022). For instance, in Italy, maximum levels of pollutant
439 concentrations for reclaimed water are defined for 55 parameters, being for many of them as strict
440 as for drinking water (Troldborg et al., 2017). Italian legislation thus follows the conventional fit-for-
441 all approach, which means that the same water quality of effluents is require regardless the purpose
442 to which reclaimed water is used (Becerra-Castro et al., 2015). This can be quite inefficient since it
443 often implies higher operating costs and intensive monitoring of the water quality. On the other
444 hand, different quality standards can be set depending on the final water reuse, following a fit-for-
445 purpose approach (Capodaglio and Olsson, 2020). This implies that the required quality could be
446 obtained without unnecessary post-treatments, thus saving operating costs and energy demands

447 (EIT Water Scarcity, 2021). The EU has clearly showed its intention to pursue the fit-for-purpose
448 approach since Regulation 2020/741 establishes and standardises the water quality limits and the
449 frequency of monitoring depending on the type of crops to be irrigated and the irrigation techniques
450 (Radini et al., 2022). This shift of approach can be very relevant to increase water reuse practices
451 since it gives more flexibility to the process and can help to diminish the overall impacts and
452 difficulties of the process. It must be clarified that the fit-for-purpose approach must be coupled to
453 the elaboration of WRRMPs with the goal to assure the safe use of reclaimed water in each case.
454 However, despite the goals to be pursued by the elaboration of WRRMPs are clear from a theoretical
455 point of view, there are still some controversies about how to develop them in a clear, efficient and
456 standard way (Radini et al., 2022). For this reason, many experts from the water sector and
457 stakeholders related to water utilities are demanding for guidelines that help them to appropriately
458 develop these WRRMPs, which are expected to be launched before the application deadline of the
459 Regulation 741/2020 for the EU members on 26 June 2023.

460 Apart from the barriers associated to excessive legal requirements, Seco et al. (2018b) also noticed
461 the lack of standardisation in the current legislation as a significant hurdle for the deployment of
462 water reuse practices. For instance, regarding fertigation (i.e., the direct application to cropland of
463 the nutrients contained in reclaimed water), legislation that clearly states and regulates this activity
464 is still lacking; although is contemplated in Regulation 741/2020 as a feasible practice to increase
465 circularity in the water reuse sector, and has been demonstrated to provide economic and
466 environmental benefits in comparison to other alternative water sources such as water transfers
467 and desalination (Jiménez-Benítez et al., 2020). As a consequence, fertigation is often underused.
468 To increase fertigation (and therefore wastewater reuse), it is important to develop some legislation
469 and/or guidelines that provides exact information about which fertigation practices are safe and
470 which of them could imply issues due to excessive nutrient addition. This legislation would aim to

471 regulate and standardise fertigation practices, analogous to what Regulation 741/2020 does with
472 irrigation practices. The support of experts on those topics in its elaboration would be therefore
473 recommended. This should be also complemented with integrated nutrient management plans that
474 would report information about maximum nutrient concentrations in reclaimed water and soils,
475 maximum amount of water and mineral fertilisers to be applied to farmlands, and water, nutrient
476 and economic balances (Radini et al., 2022; Seco et al., 2018b).

477 Similarly, there is also a current gap on specific legislation regarding wastewater treatment in
478 decentralised areas (Cipolletta et al., 2021). Around 15% of Europe population lives in remote areas
479 where sanitation, water and energy supply is often challenging, being well-established wastewater
480 treatment technologies often hard to be installed. The implementation of water treatment
481 prototypes that are able to cope with their reality often faces numerous legislative barriers that
482 hinder their deployment (Cipolletta et al., 2021). In this respect, many water experts defend that
483 decentralised systems present certain specificities that make them not comparable to common
484 centralised WWTPs. For this, the development of an Innovation Deal approach has been recently
485 recommended as a possible solution to implement policies that differentiate the legal requirements
486 to be accomplished in centralised and decentralised systems with the goal to favour the deployment
487 of decentralised wastewater treatment systems (Cipolletta et al., 2021), which could help to reduce
488 water stress in remote regions.

489 To sum up, Table 6 shows the main issues related to the techno-economic, socio-political and legal
490 aspects to be considered for the transformation of the wastewater sector.

491 [TABLE 6 NEAR HERE]

492

493 4. Water reuse sector in Italy

494 Italy is the first EU country in water withdrawal for civil use (with more than 9 billion m³·y⁻¹), and
495 the second in relative terms: 152.4 m³·inhab⁻¹ withdrawn for drinking water (The European House -
496 Ambrosetti, 2022). During the last decade, this number has decreased by 4.2%, but it is still
497 insufficient to significantly reduce the current hydric pressure on Italian water sources. In addition
498 to this, Italy ranks 18th in the EU-27(+UK) ranking in the Water Value for Sustainable Development
499 Index, a factor that evaluates water impacts on 10 of the 17 UN-Sustainable Development Goals
500 (SDGs). This means an improvement of 2 positions with respect to the previous year (The European
501 House - Ambrosetti, 2022). With respect to the use of water, irrigation is the main user like most of
502 the Mediterranean countries. According to FAO (2018), from a total of 3 892 202 ha of irrigated
503 lands in Italy, 33% of them obtain water from groundwater sources, while 67% of irrigated lands
504 uses surface water.

505 With respect to reclaimed water, water reuse solutions have grown significantly in Italy recently,
506 achieving up to 82 water reuse schemes for agricultural purposes in 2017 (WRE, 2022). Some of
507 these schemes are described in Table 7. However, it still remains as a minor water source for
508 irrigation. In fact, in some of the most important water utilities, the percentage of wastewater
509 reused does not even reach 10% of the total wastewater treated (Table 7). Although this number is
510 higher than other European countries that are normally under 5% (Radini et al., 2022), it can be
511 stated that water reuse in Italy is far from its maximum potential.

512 [TABLE 7 NEAR HERE]

513

514 With the goal to better understand some of the reasons of this current situation, as well as to
515 analyse the role of Italian water utilities in the transformation of the water reuse sector and assess
516 their expectations for the recent future, the business models of some of the most relevant Italian

517 water utilities were evaluated. Regarding their main investments for the following years, it was
518 observed that all the utilities evaluated, despite their large differences in terms of size, capacities
519 and regions of action, presented many similarities. All these companies intend to increase
520 sustainability in their operations since they are increasing the investment in decarbonisation and
521 circular economy (including water reuse) for the next years/decades. They all are also interested in
522 investing in R&D-related topics such digital tools and technologies for controlling and removing
523 pollutants. Furthermore, they generally contemplate within their business plans to follow the
524 principals agreed in the Green Deal, the Circular Economy Action Plan and to contribute to several
525 UN-SDGs of the 2030 Agenda. However, the budget dedicated to those R&D aims is still low (Table
526 8) in comparison to others. They normally prefer to dedicate more money to other budget items
527 not directly related to water reuse such as leakage detection, maintenance of facilities and water
528 networks; efficiency improvement of equipment, etc. It could be thus said that, in general, reclaimed
529 water is not the main product which utilities aim to obtain. One key aspect related to this lies on the
530 fact that Italian utilities do not have direct economic incentives to reuse water in comparison to
531 classical wastewater treatment, i.e., they do not receive extra money (from neither water
532 consumers nor public administrations) when wastewater is reused rather than only discharged.
533 More focus of Italian utilities is put on recovering by-products from wastewater such as biofuels
534 (biogas, hydrogen, etc), as they indeed provide some direct revenues to their companies. In
535 addition, investments are mainly covered by the water tariff (78%), which is one of the lowest in
536 Europe. For instance, it is half of that of France and 40% of Germany's (The European House -
537 Ambrosetti, 2022). This often disincentives water companies to transform their technologies, as
538 this means that (indirectly) they have to assume most of the investment risks. As a consequence,
539 the level of investment in the Integrated Water Service in Italy accounts for only 56% of the
540 European average (Utilitalia, 2021). To shift this current situation, Italian utilities are considering in

541 their business plans to obtain funds from the National Recovery and Resilience Plan (in Italian Piano
542 Nazionale di Ripresa e Resilienza (PNRR)). Actions such as update and improvement of structures,
543 reduction of losses in water distribution networks, digitalisation of the sector, and resilience of
544 irrigation agrosystems could be funded by PNRR. It must be noticed that those actions are mostly in
545 line with the investments previewed by the Italian water utilities in their business plans for the
546 recent future.

547 [TABLE 8 NEAR HERE]

548

549 Important to note is that all utilities agree that future efforts must be done to improve digitalisation
550 as it can enable a new, inclusive, more efficient and sustainable water management models (Martins
551 et al., 2013; Schivardi and Schmitz, 2018). However, the development of technological solutions is
552 still limited in Italy in comparison to other EU members, occupying the position 20 out of the EU-27
553 members in the Digital Economy and Society Index (DESI) (EC, 2021c). Some barriers to the
554 deployment of digital tools in the water sector are related to: i) the relatively high investment in
555 new digital equipment and resources, and in the training of their employees; ii) digital tools for
556 water management have not been traditionally considered as a priority for many companies and
557 policy makers; iii) the payback of digital investments is not immediate, so it is sometimes hard to be
558 perceived by users and/or investors; iv) limited stakeholder engagement; v) data reliability and
559 security issues; vi) sometimes limited access to reliable internet network, f.i. in decentralised
560 systems (EIT Water Scarcity, 2021; Zipper et al., 2019). From the analysis of water utilities, it was
561 observed that generally, minor companies will tend to put more efforts in more basic tools such as
562 remote reading, remote control, monitoring and digital services with users; while the biggest ones
563 will also try to develop more complex tools such as early warning systems (EWS), cloud-based
564 platforms, artificial intelligence tools, etc. The differences in the type of digital tools that companies

565 invest in seem to be more significantly influenced by the higher financial capacity of bigger
566 companies, that allow them to invest more money with lower risks than by differences in the
567 willingness of utilities to implement digitalisation. These advanced digital tools are essential for the
568 wide development of water reuse practices. For all these reasons, bigger utilities are expected to
569 increase their capacity to reuse wastewater faster than other smaller utilities that cannot (or are
570 not so willing to) promote water reuse technologies. This could be highly relevant in a future
571 scenario where water reuse practices are expected to be essential in the economy and resource
572 management of a country like Italy (EIT Water Scarcity, 2021). For instance, if sustainable policies
573 such as GPP are implemented, utilities that produce reclaimed water could have some competitive
574 advantages (f.i., in public contract acquisition) in comparison to other “less sustainable” companies.
575 However, green procurement and EU taxonomy was hardly considered in the water utilities
576 evaluated. In fact, only Gruppo Hera (the biggest utility evaluated) referred to EU taxonomy in their
577 business plans. This is an indicator that Italian water utilities do not consider green procurement as
578 an urgent topic, which can hinder the development of water reuse.

579 As already mentioned, all the actors involved in the water reuse sector (technical, economic, socio-
580 political and legal) (Figure 2) have their responsibility in the transition from WWTPs to WRF to occur
581 and need to align

582 their goals for it to occur. However, if some of these actors get stuck in the traditional way of
583 thinking, the hurdles that water reuse are currently facing will be unlikely to be overcome. In this
584 respect, the recently launched JCR report (Orveillon et al., 2022), which assessed the most
585 interesting materials to be reused, has stated that water reuse (and resource recovery from
586 wastewater) are interesting topics, but they are not the main priority in a macroscale level in
587 comparison to other wastes. This, together with not having a specific section for water in the
588 updated version Circular Economy Action Plan, suggest that water reuse is still not a central axis of

589 the European’s innovation agenda. Hence, despite the big efforts of water professionals in lobbying
 590 for the importance of water, it seems that water reuse practices will have to be developed mainly
 591 at national and regional level in the following couple of years. Water unbalanced and decentralised
 592 regions in Southern Europe seem to be the most active and the ideal actors to lead the transition to
 593 a circular wastewater sector in Europe since it could improve local economies, making them less
 594 dependent to other economic activities that are highly water consuming such as agriculture and
 595 tourism (Lavrníć et al., 2017; Ofori et al., 2021).

596
 597 Figure 2. Actors involved in the transformation of the wastewater sector.
 598

599 Conclusions

600 Current wastewater treatment sector must be transformed to be more circular and cope with the
 601 current societal and environmental demands. In this respect, wastewater reuse is a feasible option
 602 to reduce water scarcity issues, but it is still an underused practice. In Europe, Regulation related to
 603 water reuse for irrigation has been recently approved with the goal of implementing reclaimed
 604 water production by standardising its quality requirements, thus assuring the safe use of reclaimed
 605 water in irrigation. However, many wastewater treatment facilities have not been designed to
 606 achieve those quality standards. Consequently, from a technical point of view, current WWTP must

607 be implemented (or new reclaimed water facilities must be built up) with the most convenient water
608 reuse technologies that produce high-quality and safe reclaimed water with the lowest treatment
609 costs and environmental impacts. To this aim, refining, disinfection and/or advanced oxidation
610 technologies may be needed, depending on each case.

611 Simultaneously, facilities must be updated using modern digital tools that help them to improve the
612 process efficiency and assure safe reclaimed water production. To carry out so, high investment in
613 water reuse technologies is required. High surface areas and personnel formation could be also
614 needed. All these factors commonly make water utilities discourage to transform their WWTPs into
615 WRFs. Hence, the transformation of the wastewater treatment sector from linear to circular, i.e., by
616 implementing water reuse, will be only produced if it is aligned with other paradigm shifts: i) the
617 transition to “Digital Water infrastructures” must occur to improve water treatment performance,
618 and reduce process impacts and malfunctions; ii) awareness related to the “value of water” and the
619 benefits of water reuse must be raised; iii) the current negative vision of water reuse must be
620 changed by assuring safety in its use; iv) reclaimed water production must be coupled with the
621 recovery of other resources present in wastewater such as nutrients and biochemical energy; v) co-
622 investment of water infrastructures by implementing full-cost recovering policies; vi) increasing
623 incentives of water utilities by developing innovative green public procurement tools that reward
624 sustainable practices such as reclaimed water production; vii) developing legislation that
625 standardise and encourage water reuse practices, f.i., EU 741/2020 (that follows a fit-for-purpose
626 approach), or by implementing fertigation to recover nutrients from wastewater; viii) giving more
627 flexibility to decentralised wastewater treatment systems to implement water reuse practices also
628 in small populations; ix) the implementation of NEXUS thinking between water and other related
629 sectors.

630 From an Italian perspective, water utilities currently show an increasing will to transform their
631 facilities by increasing the investment in new facilities, digitalisation, and improvement of water
632 infrastructures. But even so, reclaimed water production remains as an underused practice since
633 water companies' revenues do not significantly improve when wastewater is reused instead of just
634 being discharged. To shift this current situation, other actors involved in the water reuse sector such
635 as decision makers, consumers and water stakeholders must also play a role and align their goals to
636 those of the utilities. If not, the hurdles that water reuse are currently facing will be unlikely to be
637 overcome.

638

639 [Acknowledgements](#)

640 The authors acknowledge the EU's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme for their
641 support to fund "Digital Water.City" project under Grant Agreement 820954 and Partnership on
642 Research and Innovation in the Mediterranean Area (PRIMA) for their support in the project "Safe
643 and Sustainable Solutions for the Integrated Use of Non-Conventional Water Resources in the
644 Mediterranean Agricultural Sector (FIT4REUSE)", which received funding from the Grant Agreement
645 No 1823.

646 Authors would also like to acknowledge Water Utilities HERA, CAP, ACEA, CIIP, IREN, A2A and SMAT
647 for their collaboration on the study.

648

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1086 Table 1. Refining technologies: target compounds, operating parameters and removals

TECHNOLOGY	TARGET GROUPS	TARGET POLLUTANTS	OPERATING PARAMETERS	REMOVAL	REFERENCES
Rapid sand filtration	Microplastics	Microplastics	Sand layer composed of 1 m of gravel with grain size of 3-5 mm and 0.5 m of quartz with grain size 0.1-0.5 mm.	97%	(Talvitie et al., 2017)
	Microplastics	Microplastics	Pilot-scale sand filter. Filtering area: 0.07 m ² . Treatment flow: 14.3-42.9 m ³ ·m ⁻² ·h ⁻¹	39.5 ± 34.6%	(González Camejo et al., 2022)
Dynamic membranes	Macro-pollutants	TSS, COD, TN, TP	Supporting material: 1 µm pore size; J = 14.7 LMH; Coagulant: 10 mg Al ₂ O ₃ ·L ⁻¹	65-80% (TN=16%)	(Sanchis-Perucho et al., 2022)
MF	Pathogens, CECs	Bacteria, virus PhCs, EDCs, PFCs, BTRs, BTHs	pore size: 0.20-0.45 micron pressure: 0.5 - 5 bar, flux: 65 - 85 LMH·bar ⁻¹	-	(Arvaniti et al., 2022; Nasir et al., 2022)
UF	Pathogens, CECs	E.coli, ARGs PhCs, Nonylphenol (NP), Triclosan (TCS), PFCs, BTRs, BTHs	1-100 kDa membranes Pressure: 1 bar	-	(Arvaniti et al., 2022; Nasir et al., 2022; Riquelme Breazeal et al., 2013)
	Microplastics	Microplastics	-	99%	(Ziajahromi et al., 2017)
	Microplastics	Microplastics	Pilot-scale UF membranes Membrane area: 3.4 m ² Pore size: 0.03 µm Transmembrane flux: 20-50 LMH Specific air demand: 0.1-1.2 Nm ³ ·m ⁻² ·h ⁻¹ .	-	(González Camejo et al., 2022)
AnMBR	Bacteria	T4 Phage	Nominal membrane pore size: 0.4 µm; HRT: 12 h	-	(Nasir et al., 2022)

	Microplastics	Microplastics	Nominal membrane pore size: 0.03 μm ; HRT: 6 h	94%	(Pittura et al., 2021)
AeMBR	Pathogens	Bacteria (MS-2 Phage; Somatic coliphage); Virus (Norovirus GI/GII, Adenovirus, Sapovirus Norovirus GI, Enterovirus)	Nominal membrane pore size: 0.04 μm ; HRT: 7.2-36 h	-	(Nasir et al., 2022)
	Microplastics	Microplastics	Nominal membrane pore size: 0.4 mm. HRT: 20 - 100 h; J = 5 – 12 LMH.	99.9%	(Talvitie et al., 2017)
PAC	CECs	Sulfamethoxazole, Diclofenac, Carbamazepine, PhCs, EDCs, PFCs, BTRs, BTHs	Concentration: 10-20 mg PAC·L ⁻¹ ; bulk density: 400–500 g·L ⁻¹ ; moisture: < 3%; active surface: 900 m ² ·g ⁻¹ ; iodine number: 850 mg·g ⁻¹ ; contact time: 0.3-1 h.	Sulfamethoxazole : 58–64% Diclofenac: 69% Carbamazepine: 90–92% PhCs: From 8 ± 25% (Caffeine) to 94±2% (Propanol) EDCs: 39-44% PFCs: 13-30% BTRs: 46-75% BTHs: 54-73%	(Arvaniti et al., 2022; Rizzo et al., 2020)
Horizontal flow CW	Bacteria	E.coli, Total coliform	Specific Flux 10m ³ d ⁻¹ , Area 35m ²	Total coliform: 90%; E. coli: 50%	(Mishra et al., 2018)
Subsurface flow CW	Bacteria, Virus	E.coli, Enterococci, Total coliforms, somatic coliphages, C. perfringens spores, Adenovirus	Depth of bed 0.2- 0.6m Area 1320-1733 m ² HRT: 2.3-4d	0.9-4.27 log	(Kaliakatsos et al., 2019; Rühmland and Barjenbruch, 2013; Russo et al., 2019)
	Emerging contaminants	Ibuprofen, Diclofenac, Tonalide, Triclosan, Bisphenol A	Area: 229- 317m ² , Average inflow 14m ³ d ⁻¹ with 20 pulses d ⁻¹ ;	27.3%-87.0%	(Ávila et al., 2015)

	Emerging contaminants	Microplastics	Area 500m ² , Average inflow 261m ³ d ⁻¹ (range 106-927m ³ d ⁻¹)	88%	(Wang et al., 2020)
Free water surface CW	Bacteria, Virus	E.coli, total coliforms, Enterococci, Adenovirus	Area: 1300 – 6370 m ² HRT: 3-4 days	0.6 - 3.0 log	(Kaliakatsos et al., 2019; Rühmland and Barjenbruch, 2013; Vivant et al., 2016)
Vertical flow CW	Bacteria	Total coliform, E.coli	Area 50m ² , hydraulic load 80L m ⁻² d ⁻¹ , COD load 27g m ⁻² d ⁻¹ , TSS load 5g m ⁻² d ⁻¹	2.3 - 3.2 log	(Otter et al., 2020)
Pond	Bacteria	E.coli, Enterococci	Area 1520-1550m ²	1.7-2.0 log	(Rühmland and Barjenbruch, 2013)
Ditch	Bacteria	E.coli, Enterococci	Area 3230m ²	1.6 - 1.7 log	(Rühmland and Barjenbruch, 2013)
Lagoon	Bacteria	E.coli, Total coliforms, Somatic coliphages, Enterococci, C. perfringens spores	Storage volume 60m ³ , maximum depth 1.0m, mean influent flowrate 3m ³ d ⁻¹ , HRT 20d	0.2 - 1.9 log	(Russo et al., 2019)

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1090 Table 2. Disinfection technologies: target compounds, operating parameters and removals

TECHNOLOGY	TARGET GROUP	TARGET POLLUTANTS	DOSAGE (mg·min ⁻¹ ·L ⁻¹)	REMOVAL	REFERENCES
Chlorination	Bacteria	Total coliforms	0.8-2.4 (Chlorine dioxide (ClO ₂))	2-4 log	(Tchobanoglous et al., 2014)
		Virus	5 – 13.5 (Chlorine dioxide (ClO ₂))	2-4 log	
		Protozoa	235-1000 (Chlorine dioxide (ClO ₂))	2-3 log	
		Faecal enterococci	10-60 (Hypochlorite (NaClO))	1.5-1.9 log	(Ragazzo et al., 2013)
PAA	Bacteria	E. coli	175-250	3.5-4 log	(Antonelli et al., 2013)
		Enterococci	10-99	0.2-3 log	(Maffettone et al., 2020; Ragazzo et al., 2013)
		E. coli	10-60	1.7-2.5 log	(Ragazzo et al., 2013)
		total coliforms	8-189	0.8-3.3 log	(Koivunen and Heinonen-Tanski, 2005)
		coliphages	8-189	0.2-0.9 log	(Koivunen and Heinonen-Tanski, 2005)
		Faecal Coliforms	27-52	1-2 log	(Maffettone et al., 2020)
				E. coli	10-73.8
PFA	Bacteria	Enterococci	3.5-73.8	0.3-2.47 log	(Maffettone et al., 2020; Ragazzo et al., 2013; Rocher and Azimi, 2021)
		Coliformi fecali	1.5-10	1-2.5 log	(Karpova et al., 2013; Maffettone et al., 2020)
		Clostridium perfringens	16.8-65	0.1-0.3 log	(Stüber and Miehe, 2016)
		Somatic coliphages	16.8-65	2.3-2.5 log	
OZONATION	Pathogens	E. coli	0.6-1 mgO ₃ ·mgCOD ⁻¹ ; 5 min	2 log	(Foroughi et al., 2022; Stüber and Miehe, 2016)

		E. cocci	0.6 mgO ₃ ·mgCOD ⁻¹	3 log	(Stüber and Mieke, 2016)
		Acinetobacter		3log	(Foroughi et al., 2022)
		Intestinal enterococci	1 mgO ₃ ·mgCOD ⁻¹ , 5 min	3 log	
		Eubacteria		2 log	
		Total coliforms	0.01-0.04 mg·min·L ⁻¹	2-4 log	(Tchobanoglous et al., 2014)
		Virus	0.25-0.6 mgO ₃ ·min·L ⁻¹	2-4 log	
		Protozoa	1.43-8.5 mgO ₃ ·min·L ⁻¹	2-3 log	
UV	Bacteria	E. coli, Enterococci, Clostridium perfringens, Somatic coliphages	Dose: 50-80 mJ·cm ⁻² ; Flow: 5-8.1 m ³ ·h ⁻¹ ; HRT: 5-10 s.	0.4-4.2 log	(Stüber and Mieke, 2016)
		E. coli	Dose: < 10 mJ·cm ⁻²	4 log	(Soller et al., 2017)
	Protozoa	Cryptosporidium Parvum oocysts, Giardia spp., Cryptosporidium spp.	Dose: 100-160 mJ·cm ⁻²	0.18-0.90 log	(Liberti et al., 2003)
		Cryptosporidium spp., Giardia spp.	Dose: 12 mJ·cm ⁻²	2.0-3.5 log	(Soller et al., 2017)
		Adenovirus, Norovirus, Enteric viruses	Dose: 12 mJ·cm ⁻²	0.5-1.5 log	(Soller et al., 2017)
	Virus	Polivirus	Dose: 80-100 mJ·cm ⁻²	5 log	(NWRI, 2012)
		Human adenovirus	Dose: 100 mJ·cm ⁻²	0.04-0.13 log removal	(Rodriguez-Manzano et al., 2012)
		Antibiotic resistant bacteria (ARB)	Dose: 5-40 mJ·cm ⁻²	1.1-1.4 log	(Guo et al., 2013)
	Antibiotic resistance	Antibiotic resistant genes (ARG)	Dose: 10-160 mJ·cm ⁻² , HRT: > 30 min.	52-73.5% (<40 mJ·cm ⁻²) 80-92% (160 mJ·cm ⁻²)	(Zheng et al., 2017)
			Dose: 200-400 mJ·cm ⁻²	3-4 log	(McKinney and Pruden, 2012)
UV+PAA	Bacteria	E. coli, Enterococcus spp Somatic coliphage faecal coliforms Salmonella	2-6 mg·L ⁻¹ , 6-30 mJ·cm ⁻² , 10 min	1.6-6.6 log	(Ao et al., 2021)
		Total Coliform, Faecal Coliform, E. coli	120 mJ·cm ⁻² , 5 sec, 2-4 ppm PAA	3.4-5 log	(Lubello et al., 2002)
UV+H2O2	Bacteria	E. coli	50 mg·L ⁻¹ , 676 W/m ²	5 log	(Y. di Chen et al., 2021)

		Total Coliforms Faecal Coliforms E. coli	120 mJ·cm ⁻² , 5 sec, 4.8 -9.6 ppm H ₂ O ₂ at 35%	2.8-3.6 log	(Lubello et al., 2002)
PAA+H2O2	Bacteria	Total Coliforms Faecal Coliforms E. coli	2-8 ppm PAA, 0.6-2.4 ppm H2O2, 30 min	2-4.6	(Lubello et al., 2002)
UV+O3	Bacteria	Total coliform, E. coli Enterococcus Faecalis	-	3.8-4.8 log	(Krakkó et al., 2021)

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1092 Table 3. Advanced treatment technologies: target compounds, operating parameters and removal

TECHNOLOGY	TARGET GROUP	TARGET POLLUTANTS	OPERATING PARAMETERS	REMOVAL	REFERENCES
PAA	CECs	Diclofenac, sulfamethoxazole, Carbamazepine	120-600 mg·min ⁻¹ ·L ⁻¹	52-80% (no carbamazepine removal)	(Rizzo et al., 2020)
PAA+UV	CECs	Diclofenac, sulfamethoxazole, Carbamazepine	20-50 mg·L ⁻¹ , 70 W·m ⁻²	82-100%	(Rizzo et al., 2020)
		EDC, Herbicide, Pesticide, DBP	6-20 mg·L ⁻¹ , 695-739 mJ·cm ⁻² , 2min	45-99%	(James et al., 2014)
OZONATION	CECs	Sulfamethoxazole, diclofenac, carbamazepine Bisphenol A, and others	0.12-0.61 mg O ³ ·mgCOD ⁻¹	80-100%	(Rizzo et al., 2020, 2019)
		Antibiotics: xyetetracycline (OTC), doxycycline (DTC), ciprofloxacin (CIP)	Dose: 11000-30000 mJ·cm ⁻²	98-99%	(Yuan et al., 2011)
UV	CECs	Pharmaceuticals, antibiotics, anticonvulsants, pesticides, and others.	Volume: 35 L; HRT: 15 min; Intensity: 1025 mW·cm ⁻² ; Dose: 2768 mJ·cm ⁻²	Very variable: from 4-7% for some compounds to 86- 100% for others	(Kim et al., 2009)
		PhCs, EDCs, PFCs, BTHs, Nonylphenol (NP), Triclosan (TCS)	Intensity: 70 mWs·cm ⁻²	From NR to 74±7%	(Arvaniti et al., 2022)
UV+O3	CECs	DCBQ	UV: 630 mJ·cm ⁻² , O3: 1 mg·L ⁻¹	92.4%	(Pan et al., 2022)
		Trimethoprim (TMP); primidone (PRM); sulfamethoxazole (SMZ); carbamazepine (CBZ); fluoxetine (FLU); gemfi-brozil (GMF)	O3 = 1.5-3-6 mg·L ⁻¹ ; UV = 465 mJ·cm ⁻²	15-100%	(Sgroi et al., 2021a)

O3+H2O2	CECs	Active pharmaceutical ingredients (APIs).	UV dose: 1.2 J·cm ⁻² and 6.6 J·cm ⁻² at 185 nm and 254 nm, respectively); HRT =4.75 min, 30–45 μgO ₃ ·mgCOD ⁻¹	40–100%	(Krakkó et al., 2021)
	CECs	Diclofenac, Carbamazepine	Fe: 5–10 mg·L ⁻¹ ; H ₂ O ₂ : 20–60 mg·L ⁻¹ ; pH: 2.8 or neutral; HRTs (80, 40, 20 min)	24–100%	
	CECs	Organic micropollutants	O ₃ = 13 ± 0.5 mg·L ⁻¹ , H ₂ O ₂ = 11 mg·L ⁻¹	78%	(Piras et al., 2020)
	CECs	Parabens	0.38-1.8 gO ₃ ·h ⁻¹ , 30 W low-pressure UV lamp, pH = 9	53-65%	(Asgari et al., 2019)
Photo Fenton	Bacteria	E. coli	8.5 mg L ⁻¹ H ₂ O ₂ , 0.85 mg L ⁻¹ Fe ²⁺ , pH 4, 10 -30 min	99.4-99.8%	(Y. Chen et al., 2021)
	CECs	Sulfamethoxazole Diclofenac Carbamazepine	20-50 mg H ₂ O ₂ ·L ⁻¹ ; 2-4 mg·Fe·L ⁻¹ . pH 6–7.5, 70 W·m ⁻² .	66-100	(Rizzo et al., 2020)
Solar photo-Fenton	CECs	Sulfamethoxazole Diclofenac; Carbamazepine	Fe: 5–10 mg·L ⁻¹ ; H ₂ O ₂ : 20–100 mg·L ⁻¹ ; pH: 2.8 or neutral.	24–100	(Rizzo et al., 2020)
NF		Sulfamethoxazole, Diclofenac, Carbamazepine	Filmtec NF90 MWCO = 200 Da, Flux = 18 L·m ⁻² ·h ⁻¹	-	(Mamo et al., 2018)
		Diclofenac, Carbamazepine	Flat sheet, flux = 1–3 LMH, TMP = 0.3–0.7 bar	-	(Röhricht et al., 2009)
	CECs	PhCs, EDCs, PFCs, BRTs, ABTH, BTH	Molecular weight cut-offs (MWCOs): 1 kDa	-	(Arvaniti et al., 2022)
		PPCPs	Flowrate: 0.5 L·min ⁻¹ ; Pressure: 400 kPa	-	(Shanmuganathan et al., 2015)
		Diclofenac Carbamazepine	FILMTEC NF90-4040, 200 Da	-	(Cartagena et al., 2013)
	Virus	bacteriophage Qβ virus	Flux: 19 to 61 LMH, operation pressure: 0.3 MPa	-	(Hamaguchi et al., 2019)
GAC	CECs	Sulfamethoxazole, Diclofenac, Carbamazepine	14 min EBCT.	-	(Bourgin et al., 2018)
MF-GAC	CECs	PPCPs	Flux: 2.5-10 LMH	-	(Shanmuganathan et al., 2015)

PAC	CECs	Sulfamethoxazole, Diclofenac, Carbamazepine, PhCs, EDCs, PFCs, BTRs, BTHs	Concentration: 10-20 mg PAC·L ⁻¹ ; bulk density: 400–500 g·L ⁻¹ ; moisture: < 3%; active surface: 900 m ² ·g ⁻¹ ; iodine number: 850 mg·g ⁻¹ ; contact time: 0.3-1 h.	Sulfamethoxazole: 58–64%; Diclofenac: 69%; Carbamazepine: 90– 92%; PhCs: From 8 - 25% (Caffeine) to 94±2% (Propanol); EDCs: 39-44%; PFCs: 13-30%; BTRs: 46- 75%; BTHs: 54-73%	(Arvaniti et al., 2022; Rizzo et al., 2020)
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1094 Table 4. Key performance indicators (KPI) and comparison of water reuse technologies.

	KPI	CLHORINATION	PAA	PFA	OZONE	AOPs	GAC/PAC	UV	MEMBRANE	NBS
INFRASTRUCTURE AND MANAGEMENT	SCALE OF APPLICATION	large	medium	medium	medium	large	medium	large	medium	low
	OPERABILITY	easy	easy	difficult	medium	medium	medium	easy	difficult	easy
	PLANT COMPLEXITY	medium	medium	high	high	medium/high	medium	low	high	Low
PERFORMANCES IN POLLUTANT REMOVAL	BACTERICIDE ACTION	high	high	high	high	high	low	high	high	medium
	VIRUCIDAL ACTION	medium	medium	medium	medium	high	low	medium	high	low
	PROTOZOA REMOVAL	low	low	high	high	high	low	high	high	low
	CECs REMOVAL	low	low	N.A.	high	high	medium	low	high	low
DOSAGE	DOSE – CLASS A (mg·min·L ⁻¹) ^a	100-300 ^j	210-600	20-60	50-70	N.A.	N.A.	80-100 ^b	Pore size UF/NF	N.A.
	DOSE – CLASS B (mg·min·L ⁻¹) ^a	70-150	100-300	5-20	20-30	N.A.	N.A.	60-80 ^b	Pore size UF/NF	N.A.
	DOSE – CLASS C (mg·min·L ⁻¹) ^a	30-80	50-100	<5	<10	N.A.	N.A.	30-60 ^b	Pore size MF	N.A.
	DOSE – CLASS D (mg·min·L ⁻¹) ^a	10-40	20-50	1-5	<10	N.A.	N.A.	< 30 ^b	Pore size MF	N.A.
AFFECTING PARAMETERS	SUSPENDED SOLIDS	high	low	low	high	high	high	high	high	low
	ORGANIC COMPOUNDS	high	low	medium	high	medium	high	medium	high	medium
	AMMONIA-NITROGEN	low	low	medium	low	low	low	low	low	medium

DOWN STREAM EFFECTS	BY-PRODUCTS	THMs, NDMA, HAAs	AOX	none	NDMA, bromate	none	none	none	none	none
	RESIDUAL TOXICITY	high	low	medium	medium	none	none	none	none	none
	BACTERIAL RE-GROWTH	low	high	low	low	none	N.A.	medium	medium	medium
COSTS	OPEX (€·m ⁻³)	low 0.023 ^c	low 0.023 ^c	low	medium 0.02-0.037 ^d	high	medium (0.12 ^e)	low 0.006	MF: 0.03 ^e UF: 0.03 ^e	CW:0.40 ^f 0.12 ^g 0.64 ^h 0.31 ^h 0.85 ^h HRAP:0.42 ^f 0.007 ⁱ 0.02 ⁱ
	CAPEX (€·m ⁻³)	low 0.002 ^c	low 0.002 ^c	low 0.002 ^c	high 0.003-0.006 ^d	High	low 0.20 ^e	medium 0.017-0.035 ^d	MF: 0.37 ^e UF: 0.42 ^e	CW:2.31 ^f 3.07 ^g 2.41 ^h 3.23 ^g 5.51 ^g HRAP:1.80 ^e 2.11 ^h 1.53 ^h

1095 ^a Dose of UV expressed as mWs·cm⁻²

1096 ^b (Crocetti et al., 2021)

1097 ^c (AQUAREC, 2006)

1098 ^d (Akhoundi and Nazif, 2018; Melgarejo et al., 2016)

1099 ^e (Mohamad Mazuki et al., 2020)

1100 ^f (Garfí et al., 2017)

1101 ^g (Freeman et al., 2019)

1102 ^h (Puigagut et al., 2007)

1103 ⁱ (Arashiro et al., 2018)

1104 ^j Not advisable for toxicity problems

1105 HRAP: High-rate algal pond

1106 Table 5. Environmental Indicators (EI) of water reuse technologies.

ENVIRONMENTAL INDICATORS	CLHORINATION	OZONE	AOPs	GAC	UV	MEMBRANE	NBS
Global Warming Potential (GWP) (kg CO ₂ -eq/m ³)	3.10E-02 ^{a1}	2.35E-01 ^b	7.87E-01 ^b	3.99E-01 ^{c1}	2.58E-02 ^{a3}	2.50E-01 ^d	1.74E-01 ^g
	3.88E-02 ^{a2}			1.55E-01 ^{c2}			3.49E-05 ^f
Energy consumption (KWh/m ³)	1.69E-01 ^{a1}	1.70E-01 ^b	1.10E-01 ^b		1.45E-01 ^{a3}	3.89 ^d	3.0E-01 ^f
	2.15E-01 ^{a2}		5.0E-01 ^l 5.43E+02 ^l				
Acidification (kgSO ₂ /m ³)	1.75E-04 ^{a1}	1.15E-03 ^b	4.44E-03 ^b	2.38E-03 ^{c1}	2.31E-04 ^{a3}	1.3E-03 ^d	2.67E-05 ^f
	2.98E-04 ^{a2}			0.68E-03 ^{c2}			
Abiotic Depletion Potential (ADP) (kg Sb eq./m ³)	2.24E-04 ^{a1}	-	-	3.17E-08 ^{c1}	1.87E-04 ^{a3}	-	7.46E-08 ^h
	2.81E-04 ^{a2}			5.5E-09 ^{c2}		-	
Freshwater Eutrophication Potential(FEP) (kgP eq./m ³)	1.84E-05 ^{a1}	1.23E-04 ^b	2.48E-04 ^b	1.66E-03 ^{c1}	1.72E-05 ^{a3}	2.5E-04 ^d	2.94E-05 ^f
	2.47E-05 ^{a2}			0.09E-03 ^{c2}			-
Marine eutrophication Potential(MEP) (kgN eq./m ³)	-	5.66E-05 ^b	1.08E-04 ^b	-	-	4.1E-03 ^d	5.71E-04 ^e 4.13E-05 ^k
Ecotoxicity potential (ETP)	5.51E-02 ^{a1}	1.57E-02 ^b	1.71E-02 ^b	8.62E-02 ^{c1}	4.19E-02 ^{a3}	4.2E-03 ^d	1.54E-04 ⁱ

1107	(kgDCB eq./m³)						
1108	6.53E-02 ^{a2}			1.12E-02 ^{c2}	-	-	2.08E-04 ^j
1109	Ozone Depletion						
1110	Potential (ODP)						
1111	2.35E-09 ^{a1}	2.58E-08 ^b	5.94E-08 ^b	1.76E-08 ^{c1}	1.52E-09 ^{a3}	-	2.42E-08 ^e
1112	(kg CFC-11 eq./m³)						
1113	2.54E-09 ^{a2}			1.41E-08 ^{c2}	-	-	1.93E-07 ^f

1114 a:(Meneses et al., 2010) (a1: prechlorination, a2: postchlorination, a3: chlorination+UV treatment)

1115 b: (Arzate et al., 2019) (Ozone; AOPs: solar photo-Fenton)

1116 c: (Jeswani et al., 2015) - GAC (c1: carbon no regeneration, c2: 90% carbon regeneration)

1117 d: (Carre et al., 2017) – ultrafiltration

1118 e: (Kobayashi et al., 2020)

1119 f: (Thompson et al., 2022) - Irrigation lagoons. Irrigation energy intensity includes electricity associated with pumping treated wastewater to agriculture land

1120 g: (Lam et al., 2015)

1121 h: (Corbella et al., 2017)

1122 i: (Flores et al., 2019)

1123 j: (Lourenço and Nunes, 2021)

1124 k: (Garfi et al., 2017)

1125 l: (Miklos et al., 2018)

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1127 Table 6. Evaluation of techno-economic, socio-political and legal aspects to encourage the transformation of the wastewater sector.

Aspect	Current barriers	Paradigm shifts	How these changes would encourage the transformation of the water sector	Difficulties in the implementation
Technical	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Low development of digitalisation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Deployment of digitalisation to improve water treatment performance and reduce malfunctions. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Cost reduction. - Assurance of high quality of reclaimed water. - Higher reliability of water reclaimed facilities. - Extension of infrastructures' life. - Reduction of the possibility of making mistakes. - Greater speed in decision-making. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - High investment. - Personnel training. - Continuous updating. - Low level of maturity of some digital solutions.
Economic	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - High investment in infrastructures and digital tools. - Low market value of by-products from wastewater (including reclaimed water). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Revenues from by-products obtained from wastewater. - Modern technologies to improve water quality and improve treatment performance. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Reclaimed water can be sold as wastewater by-product. - Most efficient technologies can assure the safe use of reclaimed water. - Reduction of operating costs by increasing process performance. - Reduction of pollutant, GHG emissions, energy losses and resource consumption of the water treatment process. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Risk assessment. - Reduced market of circular water by-products. - Requirement of high-skilled personnel.
Socio-Political	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Low prizes of water tariffs. - Limited support to circular water policies. - Limited awareness of issues related to water scarcity. - Mised concept of reclaimed water as competitor with potable water instead of as alternative water source. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Raise awareness. - Full-cost recovery policies. - Implementation of water policy-based tools such as green public procurement and EU Taxonomy - Implementation of NEXUS thinking. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Partial funding of water infrastructures from increased water tariff. - Water pricing encourages water saving. - Encouraging of water companies to implement sustainable processes (not only economic ones). - Development of systemic policies that considers all the sectors influencing water management. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Lack of consideration of the "real value of water". - Perception of risk in the use of reclaimed water. - Lack of knowledge related to the long-term effects of water reuse. - Lack of knowledge on the relationships between the sectors which influence water management.

- “Silo” thinking: not considering the correlation of water with other sectors.

Legal

- Legal barriers in the implementation of water reuse.
- Lack of standardisation in the water reuse sector.
- Lack of recognition of some water reuse practices such as fertigation.
- No differentiation between centralised and decentralised systems.

- Approval of EU Regulation 741/2020 by EC.
- Fit-for-purpose approach.
- Elaboration of new legislation.
- Specific requirements for decentralised systems.

- Application of EU Regulation 741/2020 in National legislations.
- Water reuse risk management plans to assure the safe use of reclaimed water.
- Circular use of water and nutrients in fertigation.
- More robust water reuse systems in decentralised and isolated regions.
- Innovation Deals to overcome legal barriers in the implementation of water reuse.

- Difficulties in the control of the accomplishment of legal requirements.
- Too conservative legal requirements in certain occasions.
- Long periods to apply EU Directives into national and regional legislation.

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1130 Table 7. Summary of some water reuse schemes implemented in Italy.

REGION	WATER UTILITY	SITE	PLANT CAPACITY (PE)	RECLAMATION FACILITY	TREATED FLOWRATE	REUSED FLOWRATE		AGRICULTURE REUSE (compared to REUSED FLOWRATE)	
				Additional treatments for reuse	m ³ ·d ⁻¹	m ³ ·d ⁻¹	%	m ³ ·d ⁻¹	%
Emilia Romagna	IREN	1. Mancasale	280 000	Sand Rapid filtration, H2O2 dosage, UV irradiation	49315	15068	31	15068	100
		2. Truccazzano	176 000	Final filtration, PAA disinfection	91675	91675	100	91675	100
		3. Basiglio	16 000	Final filtration, PAA disinfection	3605	3605	100	3605	100
		4. Binasco	30 000	Final filtration, UV disinfection	8701	8701	100	8701	100
		5. Gaggiano	10 000	Final filtration, UV disinfection	3048	3048	100	3048	100
		6. Gudo Visconti	3 000	PAA disinfection	1030	1030	100	1030	100
Lombardia	CAP	7. Lacchiarella	26 000	Final filtration, PAA disinfection	7258	7258	100	7258	100
		8. Ozzero	3 000	PAA disinfection	717	717	100	717	100
		9. San Giuliano Ovest	30 000	Final filtration, UV disinfection	12402	12402	100	12402	100
		10. Settala	58 000	Final filtration, PAA disinfection	30495	30495	100	30495	100
		11. Trezzano sul Naviglio	50 000	Final filtration, UV disinfection	22703	22703	100	22703	100
		12. Vernate	2 800	-	1081	1081	100	1081	100

	MM	13. Nosedo e San Rocco	-	-	-	24374 4	-	-	-
		14. Cremona	-	Filtration+UV	51000	13699	-	-	-
Puglia	AQUASOIL	15. Fasano	50000	Coagulation and in-line disinfection integrated with energy mixing (MITO3X®) + advanced sedimentation + final treatment with UV and/or sodium hypochlorite/PAA	7680	7680	10 0	7680	100
Basilicata	Acquedotto Lucano	16. Ferrandina	10000	light-flocculators + sand filter+ chemical disinfection	2500	30	1.2	30	100
Sicilia	-	17. Catania	432500	Sand filtration + UV	115200	-	-	-	-
	-	18. Palermo	440000	-	152000	25920	-	-	-
Sardegna	-	19. Sassari	40803	Disc filtration+ UV	-	-	-	-	-
	-	20. Cagliari	-	Sand filtration+UV+ClO2	-	95000	-	-	-
Toscana	GIDA	21. Prato	-	PAC+Coagulation/Flocculation+filtration+ Ozone	100000	-	-	-	-

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1133 Table 8. Overview of treatment, reuse capacity and investment of Italian water utilities.

Companies	Number of WWTPs	Wastewater treated (Mm³·y⁻¹)	Wastewater reused (% total)	Total investment (%total revenues)	% Investment in R&D (with respect to the total investment)	Reference
HERA	227	347.1	6.0	5,7	14.7	(Gruppo Hera, 2020)
CAP	40	346.3	34.7	11.9	3.2	(Gruppo CAP, 2020)
ACEA	484	714	1.1	24.4	38.4	(ACEA, 2020; ACEA Group, 2022)
CIIP	367	-	-	3.0	-	(CIIP, 2021)
IREN	1356	205.2	31.0	18.4	-	(Iren, 2020)
A2A	57	51	1.5	9.3	-	(A2A, 2021)
SMAT	403	358	1.1	26.2	-	(SMAT, 2020)
Total	2934	2021.6	12.3	14.1	-	

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